

THE ROLE OF CEFR IN EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

The article examines and compares students have a lot of assessment systems for getting certificate how knowledge of English language level such as IELTS, TOEFL and CEFR and so on. It mainly focuses on CEFR.

Keywords: *CEFR, information, level, conversation, strategies for communicating, language skills, phonological features, IELTS.*

CEFR was implemented in Uzbekistan in 2012 as a framework for teaching, learning, and assessing languages. CLT is employed within CEFR and the approach is much different than the GTM to language teaching that language teachers are accustomed to in Uzbekistan Within CLT, the identity of a language teacher is that of a facilitator instead as a source of information. Learning languages for communicative purposes shifts the classroom focus from the teacher to the learner; however, this shift does not mean the teacher has no role to play! A teacher's role is to guide students to become communicatively competent.

Over the past decade, the age of compulsory English learning has been reduced in many countries. Although there are various points of view about the best time to begin learning the English language, and minor differences in pupil age and program categories, the fact is that in most countries, children are learning English at younger and younger ages. In many countries, English is a compulsory subject in the early

primary grades including Uzbekistan. Even in countries where families may choose the foreign language for their children to study, English is the first choice.

The Common European Framework of Reference (usually abbreviated to the CEFR or CEF) describes what language learners can do at different stages of their learning. The CEFR is language-neutral, which means that it can be applied to any foreign language learning situation. It was originally designed as a comprehensive reference tool to promote educational transparency and to allow movement between countries for work or study within the European Union. Since its publication in 2001, the CEFR has been translated into 37 languages and its use has spread outside Europe, from Asia to Latin America, as an aid to defining levels for learning, teaching and assessment. The CEFR describes six broad levels of ability, with A1 being the lowest and C2 the highest. Learners are classified in three distinct groups: the Basic User (levels A1 and A2), the Independent User (B1 and B2) and the Proficient User (C1 and C2). As these titles suggest, learners develop not just in terms of the actual language they have available, but also in terms of their strategies for communicating. For example, in moving from basic to independent, learners will gain compensation strategies. The CEFR describes what learners can do across five language skills: Spoken Interaction, Spoken Production, Listening, Reading and Writing. For all five skills at each level, there are sets of detailed 'Can Do' statements. By dividing Speaking in two, the CEFR focuses both on the learner's production and their ability to take part in conversations and discussion. So, for example, under Spoken Interaction there is information about Turn taking: a Basic A2 learner Can use simple techniques to start, maintain or end a short conversation, whereas a Proficient C1 learner Can select a suitable phrase to preface their remarks appropriately in order to get the floor, or to gain time and keep the floor whilst thinking.

What exams are on the CEFR?

It is also clear from the teachers surveyed that many learners approach reading texts for some kind of language pay-off and without this, they may perceive that working with literature is a waste of time. In our experience, learners will see this in

terms of the lexical, grammatical or phonological features they can pick up from a text. The CEFR is not intended as a document which specifies the language items to be taught at each level but instead gives competency descriptors for each level. At a weaker B2 level, for example, a learner ‘shows a relatively high degree of grammatical control. Does not make mistakes which lead to misunderstanding’. Textbooks and syllabuses will normally specify the exact language which is to be taught at each level but literature can play a key role in helping to develop awareness, something which must be the first step towards gaining grammatical control. A detailed look at the CEFR reveals that literature is seen as a central resource in achieving its goals: ‘It is much hoped that teachers of literature at all levels will find sections of the framework relevant to their concerns and useful in making their aims and methods more transparent’.

English Profile’s main aim is to deliver the CEFR for English. It is producing Reference Level Descriptors – practical descriptions of how learners can be expected to use English at each level of the CEFR. English Profile is set to play a vital role in the production of resources for the development of curricula, wordlists, course materials and teaching guides, delivering materials of practical use for learners, teachers and, indeed, any professionals involved in language learning. The relationship between Cambridge English exams and the CEFR can be seen from a number of perspectives:

- The historical perspective
- The conceptual perspective
- The empirical perspective

There is growing evidence to support the view that the Cambridge English exams embody or reflect the CEFR in a variety of ways. The benefits of the relationship between the CEFR and Cambridge English exams are perhaps best judged by the extent to which together they enable language learning/teaching to flourish and encourage achievements to be recognised, and so enrich the lives of individuals and communities.

References:

1 Schmidt,(1990); Lewis,(1993); Fotos,(1994) for studies of how explicit consciousness raising, form-focussed tasks can had to enhanced grammatical and lexical awareness

2 <https://www.cambridgeenglish.org/exams-and-tests/cefr/>

3 CEFR, 2010, p.56/p.114

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